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Y-CHROMOSOME DNA HAPLOGROUP COMPOSITION OF THE AZERBAIJANI POPULATION: CHALLENGES AND NOTABLE FINDINGS

NURMAMMAD SHAMIL MUSTAFAYEV, ALAMDAR CHARKAZ MAMMADOV

Public Legal Entity “Institute of Molecular Biology”, Ministry of Science and Education of the Republic of Azerbaijan;

Public Legal Entity "Forensic-Medical Expertise and Pathological Anatomy Union" of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Azerbaijan;

ELSHAN ROVSHAN MAMMADOV

Public Legal Entity "Forensic-Medical Expertise and Pathological Anatomy Union" of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Azerbaijan;

GULBANU SUBHI NABIYEVA

Public Legal Entity “Institute of Molecular Biology”, Ministry of Science and Education of the Republic of Azerbaijan;

Baku State University, Ministry of Science and Education of the Republic of Azerbaijan;

Annotation: *The study of Y-chromosomal STR (Y-STR) markers has been demonstrated to provide significant insights into paternal lineage diversity, ancestry, and historical migrations. The objective of this study was to investigate the Azerbaijani population gene pool using 27 Y-STR markers with the Yfiler® Plus PCR Amplification Kit. A total of 164 unrelated males were analyzed to determine their haplotype and haplogroup compositions. The application of NEVGEN and Whit Athey (WA) predictors to the analysis of genetic data has yielded insights into the composition of the gene pool. The analysis revealed a predominance of J (~45.2%), R (~20.1%), E1b1b (~9.7%), G (~8.4%), and T (~7.1%) haplogroups, collectively accounting for ~90% of the total. This analysis also identified rarer haplogroups, including I (~3.9%), H (~1.3%), L (~2.6%), N (~0.6%), and Q (~1.3%) (~10% total). An analysis of the Y-DNA gene pool of the Azerbaijani population revealed that it is predominantly composed of haplogroups originating from various regions, including Caucasian, Near Eastern, Sami, European, Anatolian, Central Asian, and Altai. In addition, the challenges associated with haplogroup assignment and the notable findings for the DYF387S1 marker are discussed, including one-, two-, three-, and six-allelic variants. This discussion provides insights into the complex genetic structure of the Azerbaijani male population.*

Keywords: *Y-chromosome, haplotype, haplogroup, predictor, Azerbaijan population, Y-STR*

INTRODUCTION

The determination of both haplotype and haplogroup composition using Y-chromosomal Y-STR markers is of significant importance. The findings of such studies have been widely applied in practical contexts, including forensic and criminal investigations, as well as genealogical and medical research. Given that the Y chromosome is transmitted exclusively along the paternal lineage, these markers have become essential tools for the study of kinship relationships, including those between father-son, brother-brother, and grandfather-grandson. These markers have also been instrumental in the reconstruction of genealogical trees, the study of the ethnogenesis of various populations, and the analysis of historical migrations and related population genetic phenomena.

Previous studies have examined the Y-DNA polymorphism of the Azerbaijani population, with various researchers either studying it independently or in conjunction with neighboring populations in the region, including the Caucasus, Turkey, and Iran [1, 2, 10, 14, 15, 16, 18, 19, 20]. Furthermore, data obtained using various Y-DNA panels, ranging from 12 to 111 markers, within the framework of the Azerbaijan Family Tree DNA Project, have been analyzed in silico for the Azerbaijani population [1, 5]. Nevertheless, these studies cannot be regarded as wholly satisfactory for several

reasons. First, the sample sizes utilized are not sufficiently representative, and the sampling procedures are sometimes questionable. Secondly, a significant number of published studies do not include Azerbaijani authors, and the interpretation of results in some publications reflects bias, occasionally influenced by certain geopolitical interests [25]. It is noteworthy that we have also investigated the Y-DNA gene pool of the Azerbaijani population using kits including different numbers of Y-STR markers (17 and 27). Some of the results from this investigation have been incorporated into the Y-STR Haplotype Reference Database (YHRD, <https://yhrd.org/>) [7, 11, 12, 13].

Azerbaijan, historically recognized as the "Gateway to the East," occupies a pivotal position at the intersection of major trade routes, including the Silk Road and the North-South Corridor. The territory of the republic has a long history of human migration, leading to the cultural and ethnic diversification of the population. Furthermore, numerous wars have contributed to the shaping and enrichment of the genetic composition of the population. The primary objective of the present study was to investigate Y-chromosomal haplotype diversity and haplogroup composition in a sample of the Azerbaijani population. The investigation was conducted using the Yfiler® Plus PCR Amplification Kit, which represents 27 Y-STR loci. As is well established, precise haplogroup assignment is only possible through the use of Y-SNP markers, utilizing various Y-SNP panels or sequence-based kits. However, due to the high cost and time-consuming nature of these analyses, several predictors (NEVGEN, Whit Athey) have been developed to infer haplogroups from Y-STR profiles. The accuracy of these predictors is lower compared to SNP-based analyses, and in some cases, results from different predictors may even conflict. Consequently, the present study principally focuses on the challenges encountered during haplogroup assignment and the notable observations identified in the course of the analysis.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study included 164 healthy adult male Azerbaijani citizens whose ancestors had lived in the country for several generations. Sample collection was carried out on a voluntary basis in accordance with international ethical standards. All experimental procedures were performed following standard methodologies and relevant regulatory requirements. DNA was extracted using the PrepFiler DNA Extraction Kit (Applied Biosystems, Life Technologies, USA), and the quality and purity of the DNA were assessed with the QuantStudio 5 Real-Time PCR System (Applied Biosystems, USA). Amplification and denaturation were performed using the ProFlex PCR System (Applied Biosystems, USA). Genotyping was conducted using the Yfiler® Plus PCR Amplification Kit according to the manufacturer's instructions [22], and the results were analyzed with GeneMapper ID-X software. Haplogroup assignment was performed using two different predictors: NEVGEN [21] and Whit Athey's (WA) Haplogroup Predictor [24]. More detailed versions of the haplogroup tree can be found at International Society of Genetic Genealogy (ISOGG) Y-DNA Haplogroup Tree [6].

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Given the potential for disparate predictors to yield divergent haplogroup assignments, the determination of haplogroups was conducted through the utilization of two distinct predictors. In instances of conflict, priority was accorded to the predictor exhibiting superior reliability. The results of the NEVGEN predictor, which has been demonstrated to demonstrate optimal performance for populations from the Caucasus, Europe, and the Middle East, were considered primary. With the exception of a limited number of cases, the confidence level of haplogroup assignment ranged from 85% to 100%. In the examined sample of Azerbaijani males, the most prevalent haplogroups were E1b1b (~9.7%), G (G1 ~1.3%, G2 ~7.1%, total ~8.4%), J (J1 ~16.1%, J2 ~29.1%, total ~45.2%), R (R1a ~7.1%, R1b ~11.6%, R2 ~1.3%, total ~20.1%), and T (~7.1%), with a total frequency of ~90%. The remaining haplogroups I (~3.9%; I1 ~1.3%, I2 ~2.6%), H (~1.3%), L (~2.6%), N (~0.6%), and Q (~1.3%) accounted for ~10% of the sample. As anticipated, the Y-DNA gene pool of the Azerbaijani population is predominantly composed of haplogroups originating from Caucasian, Near Eastern, Sami, European, Anatolian, Central Asian, and Altai regions.

The results of the study indicate that both haplotype and haplogroup diversity are high in the examined population. These results can be attributed to historical migrations, gene flow, and ethnic

admixture. The most prevalent haplogroups observed are indicative of the region's historical and present-day demographic processes, thereby elucidating genetic affinities with neighboring populations. The elevated degree of polymorphism observed among Y-STR markers is indicative of a remarkably diverse genetic composition within the population under study. This finding facilitates a comprehensive and reliable characterization of the population's genetic landscape, thereby offering significant insights into its historical and genetic evolution.

As previously mentioned, two predictors were used to enhance the reliability of haplogroup assignments. The following table presents the signature alleles employed by the NEVGEN and Whit Athey (WA) haplogroup predictors, which are based on statistically dominant or, in other words, modal rather than deterministic values.

Table 1. List of dominant signature alleles used by predictors for haplogroup assignment

Y-STR marker	Haplogroups												
	E	H	G1	G2	I1	I2	J1	J2	L	N	Q	R	T
	Alleles												
DYS393	13	14	13	13	13	13	12	12	12	13	13	13	13
DYS390	24	25	23	23-24	23	24	23	24	23	23	23	24	23
DYS19	14	15	14	14	14	14	14	14	14	14	13	14	14
DYS391	10	11	10	10	10	11	10	10	10	10-11	10	11	10
DYS385a/b	16-19	15-18	14-16	14-15	14-14	14-15	14-17	14-15	14-17	14-14	14-14	11-14	14-16
DYS426	11	12	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	12	11
DYS388	12	13	12	12	12	12	15-17	13-15	13-14	12	12	12	13
DYS439	12	11	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12
DYS389I	13	14	13	13	13	13	12-13	13	13	13	13	13	13
DYS392	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	13	11	11	11
DYS389II	29	30	29	29	29	30	28-29	29	29	29	29	29	29
DYS458	15-17	17	15	15-16	14	15	17-19	15-16	16-17	14	14	16	15
DYS459a/b	9-10	9-10	9-10	9-10	9-10	9-10	9-10	9-10	9-10	9-10	9-10	9-10	9-10
DYS455	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11
DYS454	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11
DYS447	25	25	24-25	24-25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25
DYS437	14	15	14	14	14	14	15	14	14	14	14	15	14
DYS448	20	19	20	19-20	20	19	20	19-20	20	20	20	19	20
DYS449	30-32	31-33	29-31	29-31	29	30	29-31	30-32	30-32	29	29	30	30
DYS464a-d	15-17-17	15-16-17-18	14-15-16-17	14-15-15-16	14-15-15-15	14-15-15-16	15-16-17-18	14-15-16-17	14-15-16-17	14-14-15-15	14-14-15-15	13-14-15-16	14-15-16-17
DYS460	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
DYS481	22	21	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	23	22

DYS520	21	21	21	21	21	21	21	21	21	21	21	21	21
DYS518	37	37	37	37	37	37	37	37	37	37	37	38	37
DYS570	18	19	18	18	18	18	19	18	18	18	18	19	18
DYS576	18	19	18	18	17	18	19– 20	18	18	17	17	19	18
YGATAH4	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11

Since haplogroup predictors prioritize different Y-STR alleles, haplogroup assignments can, on occasion, differ. In addition, the accuracy of haplogroup determination depends on the regional context. In order to maximize concordance between the two predictors, we used the “general level” model was used, including 23 markers for the NEVGEN predictor, and the “equal priors” model was implemented across all regions for the WA predictor. Discrepancies between the predictors were observed during haplogroup assignment in our study. In this section, we present a series of case studies that exemplify the range of these phenomena.

For example, sample 1 was assigned by the NEVGEN predictor to haplogroup J1a2a1a2 P58 with ~95% probability, whereas the WA predictor assigned it to J1 with 100% probability until allele 11 at the DYS533 marker was included, after which it was reassigned to E3b with ~91% probability. Sample 5 was classified by NEVGEN as J2a1 PF5087>Z7430 with ~42% probability (58% corresponding to subclades unsupported by the predictor), while WA initially assigned it to J2a1b with 93% probability, and after inclusion of the DYS533 allele 11, it was reassigned to E3b (~63%), with other possible haplogroups being G2 (~18%) and I1b1 (~19%).

One of the most striking results was observed for sample 13: NEVGEN assigned it to L1c M357 with ~99% probability, whereas WA gave completely different results, assigning it to haplogroup Q with ~99% probability both before and after inclusion of the DYS533 allele 11. Similarly, in sample 26, NEVGEN assigned it to T >> CTS11451 with ~85% probability before and ~90% after inclusion of allele 12 at DYS533, whereas WA assigned it to K2 with 100% probability before inclusion and, after inclusion, to J2a1k (~66%) and E3a (~31%).

These examples demonstrate that even widely used predictors can yield different haplogroup assignments. While the DYS533 marker exerts a negligible influence on NEVGEN results, it demonstrates a substantial impact on WA assignments. The inclusion of this marker frequently results in the manifestation of haplogroups that diverge from the results obtained by NevGen, including E (E3a, E3b), Q, I1b1, and, less frequently, G2 or J2a. Overall, NEVGEN is considered more precise for the Caucasus region, while WA demonstrates superior performance for European and Near Eastern populations. Additionally, NEVGEN frequently offers high-probability assignments for subclades, a development that is of considerable significance. Consequently, the results of the NEVGEN study were accorded greater weight in our analysis.

Another notable finding of the study was related to the DYF387S1 Y-STR marker, which is typically represented by two alleles on the Y chromosome. In the present analysis, single-copy, three-copy, and six-copy variants were observed. The detection of a single allele indicates that the Y-chromosome copies of the locus share the same repeat unit and may reflect the loss of one paralogous copy (deletion) or the conversion of an unamplifiable copy into a null allele. Conversely, the presence of three or six alleles suggests the emergence of additional copies of the locus with different repeat units, reflecting copy number variation (CNV). The following table offers a concise overview of the observed cases.

Table 2. Observed variants of the DYF387S1 Y-STR marker*

Sample No	Allele
Monoallelic variants	
30, 43, 114, 143, 159	35
6, 7, 13, 84, 100, 116	36
16, 17, 26, 33, 34, 71, 76, 78, 91, 107, 108, 113, 122, 134, 138, 158, 162	37
35, 36, 40, 62, 64, 117, 146, 151, 152, 153	38

4, 59, 110, 136, 141	39
80, 103, 137	40
25	41
Triallelic variants	
14	36-38-41
87	38-39-40
123	36-37-38
125	37-38-40
Hexallelic variant	
27	36-37-38-40-41-42
<i>* Diallelic variants were considered normal and therefore are not shown in the table</i>	

As shown in Table 2, the frequency of single-copy (monoallelic) variants of the locus in the studied population sample is remarkably high, reaching approximately 25%. The monoallelic manifestation of this Y-STR marker in our population may be primarily attributable to the presence of two copies of the locus, each possessing an identical repeat number, with the second copy emerging through complete duplication. This finding stands in contrast to the prevailing literature on the subject, which considers monoallelic variants of this Y-STR marker to be rare, with observed frequencies not exceeding 0.1–1.0% in practice [3, 4, 8, 9, 17, 23]. It should be noted that the DYF387S1 Y-STR marker is not included in either the NEVGEN or WA predictors used for haplogroup assignment. Consequently, the alleles of this locus did not exert an influence on haplogroup determination.

CONCLUSIONS

Geographically, Azerbaijan is located at the crossroads of major trade routes such as the Silk Road. Throughout history, the region has been a significant nexus for large-scale migrations and a site of conflict for numerous empires. From a genetic perspective, it is indicative of a convergence zone of Caucasian, Central Asian, Middle Eastern, and European gene flows. A multitude of studies have demonstrated that historical migrations, gene flow, and ethnic admixture have culminated in a remarkably diverse haplotype and haplogroup composition within the studied population, as would be anticipated.

The predictive capabilities of Haplogroup predictors, such as NEVGEN and Whit Athey, have been demonstrated to yield high-confidence results in numerous instances. However, certain inconsistencies observed in haplogroup assignments indicate that, for more reliable and accurate determination, haplogroup classification should preferably be performed using haplogroup-specific SNP markers or sequencing-based approaches.

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